

THE SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION ON EDUCATIONAL TUTELARY/SOCIO- EDUCATION MEASURES: DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PORTUGAL AND BRAZIL

PRODUCCIÓN CIENTÍFICA SOBRE MEDIDAS DE TUTORÍA/SOCIOEDUCATIVAS:
DIFERENCIAS ENTRE PORTUGAL Y BRASIL

A PRODUÇÃO CIENTÍFICA SOBRE MEDIDAS TUTELAR/SOCIOEDUCATIVAS:
DIFERENÇAS ENTRE PORTUGAL E BRASIL

Beatriz Nascimento Leite ¹
Willian Lazaretti da Conceição ²
Rubia Fernanda Quinelatto ³

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Abstract

The present study aims to identify potential differences between educational tutelary measures and Brazilian socio-educational measures concerning adolescents in conflict with the law, by comparing the documents issued by the National Socio-Educational Service System - SINASE and the Directorate-General for Reintegration and Prison Services - DGRSP. Furthermore, it analyzes the academic production from 2000 to 2021 regarding this subject, with a focus on the Portuguese context. The qualitative methodology employed is a literature review, which made it possible to achieve these objectives. The initial conclusions show that Portuguese scientific production is inferior to Brazilian production on the topic of socio-education. Additionally, a significant presence of works from the field of psychology was identified within this subject, revealing a pathological character associated with adolescents in situations of multiple vulnerabilities.

Keywords: Educational tutelary measures; Socio-education; Academic Production; Portugal.

Resumen

El presente estudio tiene como objetivo identificar posibles diferencias entre las medidas tutelares educativas y las socioeducativas brasileñas en lo que respecta a los adolescentes en

¹ Graduated in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Pará. Member of the Study and Research Group Education and Social Justice.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8020-6786> Contact: bianasle@gmail.com

² Postdoctoral student at the Interdisciplinary Center for Social Sciences at the University of Évora. Doctorate in Education from the State University of Campinas, with equivalence from the Universidade Nova de Lisboa. Professor no Programa de Pós-graduação em Currículo e Gestão da Escola Básica da Universidade Federal do Pará e no Programa Mestrado Profissional em Educação Física da Universidade Federal do Ceará. Leader of the Study and Research Group on Education and Social Justice.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8143-6524> Contact: lazaretti@ufpa.br

³ Post-doctorate in Education from the University of São Paulo. Doctorate in Education from the Federal University of São Carlos. Federal Servant at the Administrative Dean's Office of the Federal University of São Carlo. Integrante do Grupo de Estudos e Pesquisas GEPÊPrivacão.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0827-3869> Contato: rubiafq@gmail.com

conflicto con la ley, comparando los documentos emitidos por el Sistema Nacional de Atención Socioeducativa - SINASE y la Dirección General de Reinserción y Servicios Prisionales - DGRSP. Además, se analiza la producción académica en el período de 2000 a 2021 sobre el tema, con un enfoque en la realidad portuguesa. La metodología cualitativa utilizada es la revisión de literatura, que ha permitido alcanzar dichos objetivos. Las primeras conclusiones demuestran que la producción científica portuguesa es inferior a la brasileña en lo que respecta al tema de la socioeducación; además, se identificó una gran presencia de trabajos del campo de la psicología dentro de este tema, mostrando un carácter patológico asociado al adolescente en situación de múltiples vulnerabilidades.

Palabras clave: Medidas de tutela educativa; Socioeducación; producción académica; Portugal.

Resumo

O presente estudo tem como objetivo identificar potenciais diferenças entre as medidas tutelares educativas e as socioeducativas brasileiras, no que tange a adolescentes em conflito com a lei, comparando os documentos emitidos pelo Sistema Nacional de Atendimento Socioeducativo - SINASE e Direção-Geral de Reinserção e Serviços Prisionais - DGRSP. Além disso, analisa a produção acadêmica no recorte temporal de 2000 a 2021, a respeito do tema com foco na realidade portuguesa. A metodologia qualitativa utilizada é a revisão de literatura que viabilizou alcançar tais objetivos. As primeiras conclusões demonstram que a produção científica portuguesa é inferior à brasileira no que diz respeito ao tema da socioeducação, além disso identificou-se uma presença muito grande de trabalhos do campo da psicologia dentro deste tema, mostrando um caráter patológico associado ao adolescente em situação de múltiplas vulnerabilidades.

Palavras-chave: Delinquência Juvenil; Socioeducação; Produção acadêmica; Portugal.

Introduction

The present work aims to identify potential differences between educational tutelary measures and Brazilian socio-educational measures concerning adolescents in conflict with the law, by comparing the documents issued by the Directorate-General for Reintegration and Prison Services – DGRSP and the National Socio-Educational Service System - SINASE. It also seeks to put the reality of Portuguese socio-education in perspective compared to the Brazilian context, based on the guiding question: “What is the state of scientific production in Portugal regarding juvenile delinquency?”

“Sulear,” a word not found in Portuguese dictionaries, was conceived by Paulo Freire (1997) in his book *Pedagogy of Hope*. The intention is to ideologically counter the word “nortear” (“to guide” or “to direct”), which references the North as a point of reference. According to Freire, there is a need to detach from Eurocentric (global North)

ideas when discussing the reality of countries in the global South. Since the present research was conducted on Brazilian soil by Brazilian researchers, the worldview embedded between the lines of this work is grounded in anti-colonialist thought.

The idea of researching the Portuguese reality stems from a sense of curiosity. Brazil, as a colonized country, has its own approach to justice intervention in cases of adolescents breaking the law; however, what does Portugal do? How does it do things differently? Is it possible to use its reality as a model? Additionally, the research also considered Portugal's scientific contributions to the topic: what are Portugal's contributions to the ideological discussion of juvenile delinquency?

Portugal was considered for this comparison precisely because of the colonizer-colonized relationship between the two countries. The intention is to provoke critical thinking regarding their respective realities, their challenges, and how they are addressed. How does a colonizing country compare with its colonized counterpart? Is there an equivalent relationship between them?

These questions feed the state of curiosity that led to the conception and execution of the original idea for this article. Thus, the need arose to investigate these issues in depth in order to better understand the Brazil/Portugal relationship and how each country deals with juvenile delinquency, while also, of course, contributing to the scientific production on the subject.

The research was conducted through a literature review on the digital platforms Google Scholar and the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal - RCAAP. The study delves into the discussion on Brazilian socio-education, taking into account the Portuguese data collected, not only from scientific production but also from the infrastructure of the Portuguese socio-educational system, in order to understand the differences and similarities between the two countries.

Socio-education in Brazil has siphons its theoretical support from two documents: the Statute of the Child and Adolescent (Brasil, 1990) and the National Socio-Educational Service System - Sinase (Brasil, 2006, 2012), both of which are laws that establish a rule guide for socio-educational measures in the country.

The Statute of the Child and Adolescent (Brazil, 1990) provides for the protection of these individuals' basic rights, including the right to education, the right to health, and the right to professional training. When the first is neglected, along with others, many children and adolescents are exposed to the world of crime, “[...] experiencing its ease and hardships, which will leave scars on their life path. And consequently, the social outcome: supervised freedom for those who find themselves in conflict with the law” (Quinelatto, 2013, p. 38).

Before delving into the discussion on socio-educational measures and their counterpart in the Portuguese context, it is important to establish the difference between two terms used concurrently in the Brazilian theoretical field: youth and adolescence. According to Freitas (2005), the terms:

sometimes overlap, sometimes constitute distinct yet complementary fields, and at other times, they reflect a dispute over different approaches. However, the differences and connections between the two terms are not clear, and often the existing disputes remain hidden in the imprecision of the terms (Freitas, 2005, p. 6 apud Dias, 2011, p. 26).

For socio-historical psychology, the adolescent phase is viewed as a historical construct that takes into account the economic, social, and cultural context in which it is situated. This perspective on adolescence rejects the notions of naturalization, universalization, and pathologization of this phase (Cruz, 2010; Meinerz, 2009; Davila Leon, 2005; Bock; Furtado; Teixeira, 1999; Melucci, 1997; Peralva, 1997; Abramo, 1994 apud Dias, 2011, p. 27).

The critiques of viewing adolescence as universal and natural are based on the contradiction of the idea of the incompleteness of the human being, as expressed in the quote: “[...] no one is born fully formed. We gradually shape ourselves through the social practices in which we participate” (Freire, 2007, p. 81).

For Freire, “[...] education is possible for humans because they are unfinished and aware of their incompleteness” (Freire, 1997, p. 27-28). Thus, it is not possible to accept a conception of adolescence that does not take into account the concrete reality of each individual (Quinelatto, 2021, 2022).

In Brazil, according to the Statute of the Child and Adolescent (Brazil, 1990), Socio-Educational Measures (MSE) are applicable to adolescents who commit unlawful acts and should be applied only after due legal process. These measures are outlined in Article 112 of the Statute of the Child and Adolescent and include: I - warning; II - obligation to repair the damage; III - community service; IV - assisted freedom; V - placement in a semi-liberty regime; VI - internment in an educational facility.

However, the socio-educational measure of deprivation of liberty must adhere to the principles of brevity, exceptionality, and respect for the peculiar condition of a developing person.

Still within the Brazilian context, Article 19 of Sinase outlines the following objectives: I - to contribute to the organization of the socio-educational service network; II - to ensure rigorous knowledge about the actions of socio-educational services and their results; III - to promote the improvement of the quality of management and socio-educational services; and IV - to provide information about socio-educational services. According to Article 18 of the same law, this evaluation cannot exceed intervals of more than three years.

Comparatively, the Educational Tutelary Law - LTE No. 166/99, of September 14 (Portugal, 1999), operates within the context of socio-education in the Portuguese reality. According to the Portuguese Civil Code (Portugal, 1966), as stated in Article 122: "A minor is someone who has not yet reached the age of 18." Based on this definition, minors who have committed acts classified by criminal law as crimes are addressed. Thus, adolescents who have violated Portuguese law, at the time of the offense, and who are between the ages of 12 and 16 are subject to the educational tutelary process. The execution of tutelary measures can last until the individual turns 21, at which point it must cease, according to Article 5 of the Educational Tutelary Law.

The sections that divide this article are, respectively, legal provisions: similarities and differences, methodology, results and discussions, and final considerations. In establishing the division of sections, emphasis was placed on the cohesion and logical and argumentative construction of the text, as the structure utilized by the authors becomes evident throughout the reading of this research.

Legal Provisions: Similarities and Differences

Educational tutelary measures are classified in Article 4 of the Educational Tutelary Law as follows: “a) Admonition; b) Deprivation of the right to drive mopeds or to obtain a license to drive mopeds; c) Compensation to the victim; d) Performing economic contributions or tasks for the community; e) Imposition of conduct rules; f) Imposition of obligations; g) Attendance at training programs; h) Educational support; i) Internment in an educational center. 2 - The measure provided for in item i) of the previous number is considered an institutional measure, while the others are considered non-institutional. 3 - The measure of internment in an educational center is applied according to one of the following execution regimes: a) Open regime; b) Semi-open regime; c) Closed regime.

A comparative table between the socio-educational measures from each country, highlighting their similarities, is presented below:

Table 1 - Table referring to the comparisons between socio-educational measures in Brazil and Portugal.

SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL MEASURES (MSE)	EDUCATIONAL TUTELARY MEASURES (MTE)
WARNING	ADMONITION
OBLIGATION TO REPAIR THE DAMAGE	COMPENSATION TO THE VICTIM
COMMUNITY SERVICE	PERFORMING ECONOMIC CONTRIBUTIONS OR TASKS FOR THE COMMUNITY

Source: The Authors, 2024.

It is possible to observe that out of the six socio-educational measures, only three (warning, obligation to repair the damage, community service) have a similar measure in the Portuguese context. The remaining three pertain to Assisted Freedom, the semi-liberty regime, and internment in an educational facility, which are more rigorous measures applied only in cases deemed serious according to the Brazilian constitution.

In the Brazilian context, no equivalent to the stages found in the educational tutelary measures was identified. There are six measures to be implemented, in addition to those mentioned in the table above, before the severity of the penalty is increased.

Alongside the differences between the measures, there are inconsistencies in the available data on the current situation in Brazil regarding the number of adolescents serving socio-educational measures compared to the data in the Portuguese context. This issue is particularly evident in the outdated Brazilian data relative to the more current Portuguese information, as will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

In Brazil, the last annual survey of Sinase was conducted in 2017, highlighting the government's neglect in keeping this data up to date. In 2020, a research report evaluating Sinase⁴ was prepared by the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS) in collaboration with the Ministry of Women, Family, and Human Rights, which gathered some data on the Socio-Educational System. However, some responses varied and could not be used in the study because each administration applied its own criteria for counting, making it challenging to establish a consistent standard among the collected data. Additionally, the variation in responses to the researchers' questions was substantial, particularly regarding absolute numbers (budget, number of adolescents served, gender breakdown, etc.), which further complicated the data collection process.

The inconsistency in the responses evidently hampers the efforts of both researchers and practitioners in the field, who depend on accurate data to understand the actual state of the Socio-Educational System in the country. Additionally, it impacts the general population, as adolescents in detention are part of a society that is built and experienced collectively.

The researchers at UFRGS emphasize the need for standardization in data collection, including temporal coverage (day, month, or year), frequency of updates, etc., among the units of the Brazilian Socio-Educational System, so that in the future, these numbers can be more easily visualized.

In Portugal, data collection is the responsibility of the Directorate-General for Reintegration and Prison Services (DGRSP), an agency under the Portuguese Ministry of Justice, as outlined in Decree-Law No. 123/2011 (Portugal, 2011), with its organizational structure regulated by Decree-Law No. 215/2012 (Portugal, 2012). This agency is

⁴ Disponível em: https://www.ufrgs.br/cegov/files/pub_157.pdf

responsible for crime prevention, execution of sentences, social reintegration, and management of the educational tutelary and prison systems. It publishes monthly statistics related to the country's educational centers, highlighting the difference in approaches between Brazil and Portugal regarding the updating of data on the reality of adolescents deprived of their liberty in their respective territories.

Based on the information presented, this article aimed to map and identify, through a literature review, research regarding adolescents serving educational tutelary measures. The purpose of the research is to observe what Portugal is doing and producing in the context of socio-educational research and to compare it with Brazil, aiming to establish similarities and differences in the regulation of the execution of measures (MSE and MTE) and the documents generated by the respective institutions.

Methodology

The present qualitative research is based on the Literature Review (Brizola, Fantin, 2016), which seeks to provide an overview of the scientific studies conducted on the topic of educational tutelary measures.

The time frame selected spans from 2000, one year after the establishment of the Educational Tutelary Law (LTE) in Portugal, to 2021. This historical period was chosen to maximize the number of published works available for analysis, as attempts to focus on earlier time frames yielded few results.

On the Scientific Electronic Library Online-SciELO Portugal⁵, no results were found after entering the descriptor “*educational tutelary measures.*” The same was true for the descriptor “*educational tutelary law,*” which also returned no results. The search was attempted again with “*MTE,*” the abbreviation for educational tutelary measures, but still yielded no results. Another attempt was made with the descriptor “*youth in conflict with the law,*” which also produced no results. In light of this, it was decided not to use this platform for the research and to seek alternative options.

⁵ <https://scielo.pt/>

The research conducted on the *Google Scholar*⁶ platform used the same descriptors, applying only the time filter (2000-2021). The search for “*educational tutelary measures*” yielded approximately 24,400 results; “*educational tutelary law*” returned around 27,100 results; and “*youth in conflict with the law*” generated about 237,000 results. It was evident that the number of results obtained was very high, making it impractical to conduct the proposed research within the allocated timeframe. Therefore, to better filter the results, the decision was made to combine the descriptors into a single search: “*educational tutelary measures and educational tutelary law and youth in conflict with the law,*” which yielded approximately 4,900 results.

The descriptors “*educational tutelary measures + youth in conflict with the law*” were tested, yielding approximately 16,800 results. Lastly, an additional descriptor was added to filter documents related to education: “*educational tutelary measures and youth in conflict with the law and school education,*” which presented approximately 16,300 results. The final combination of descriptors was “*educational tutelary measures + educational tutelary law + youth in conflict with the law + Portugal,*” resulting in approximately 2,760 results—a more manageable number, though still high, for further analysis.

Below is Table 2, which illustrates the research conducted:

Table 2 – 1st Google Scholar search:

DESCRIPTORS	RESULTS
Educational tutelary measures	≅ 24,400 results
Educational tutelary law	≅ 27,100 results
Youth in conflict with the law	≅ 237,000 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law	≅ 4,900 results
Educational tutelary measures + Youth in conflict with the law	≅ 16,800 results
Educational tutelary measures + Youth in conflict with the law + School education	≅ 16,300 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal	≅ 2,760 results

Source: The Authors, 2024.

⁶ <https://scholar.google.com.br/>

The number of results was substantial enough to proceed to the next stage of the research, which involved summarizing the data and applying inclusion and exclusion criteria. Therefore, the search was repeated on the same platform, adding descriptors that could help narrow down the results. For this, the descriptors “Portugal,” “journals,” and “systematic review” were chosen.

Presented below is Table 3, which illustrates the second search conducted:

Table 3 – 2nd Google Scholar search.

DESCRIPTORS	RESULTS
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + journals	≅ 615 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + systematic review	≅ 1,090 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + systematic review + journals	≅ 301 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + systematic review + public policies	≅ 1,050 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + journals + public policies	≅ 609 results
Educational tutelary measures + Educational tutelary law + Youth in conflict with the law + Portugal + journals + systematic review + public policies	≅ 299 results

Source: The Authors, 2024.

The final result of 299 works was deemed manageable for continuing the research. Duplicated works, books and book chapters, publications unrelated to the topic, and research areas outside of education were included in the exclusion criteria. Regarding the inclusion criteria, only indexed journals and works analyzing the Portuguese context were selected.

After applying these criteria to the collected works, it became evident that most focused on the Brazilian context, with only two works meeting the established criteria. Given this limitation and the scarcity of results on the SciELO Portugal platform, a search was conducted on Google for journal databases specific to Portugal. This led to the discovery of the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal (RCAAP), where a third search was performed for published works on the topic within the time frame of 2000-2021.

The search conducted in the RCAAP utilized the descriptors “*educational tutelary measures*,” “*educational tutelary law*,” and “*juvenile delinquency + Portugal*.” The search in Google Scholar indicates that the descriptor “*youth in conflict with the law*” is associated with Brazilian research, while Portuguese studies tend to use “*juvenile delinquency*” as a descriptor.

The selection of descriptors for the research was made following a brief preliminary review, during which the repetition of certain terms was identified, either in the keywords or in the titles of the observed works. Therefore, the decision to use “*juvenile delinquency*” as a descriptor for the research in this paper was based on an analysis of the terms used in documents related to the topic of socio-education, rather than arising from a subjective perspective.

In light of this, it is pertinent to discuss the meaning of the word *delinquência* (delinquency) when used to describe a teenager in a situation of deprivation of liberty. According to the Online Portuguese Dictionary (Dicio, 2024), *delinquência* is grammatically classified as a feminine noun with three definitions: 1) the action or effect of delinquency; 2) an act that consists of opposing and/or resisting regulations, norms, and laws (moral); offense; 3) criminality; lack of obedience to the law; infringement. From these definitions, it is understood that when the word “*delinquência*” is used to refer to a teenager’s actions, it carries a significant pejorative and derogatory connotation.

In addition to the aforementioned descriptors, filters for the time frame (2000-2021), open-access documents, theses, dissertations, and articles were applied as inclusion criteria. The search platform itself offers these filters. For the exclusion criteria, books, book chapters, magazines, reports, restricted-access documents, duplicates, off-topic materials, and documents that did not analyze the Portuguese context were excluded.

Results and discussion

The discovery of a Portuguese research tool helped guide a new search. The tool in question is the *Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal* (RCAAP), and the descriptor “*educational tutelary measures*” was used, considering that this was a

decisive descriptor in narrowing down the searches conducted on the other search platform.

For the research, filters available on the search tool itself were used, including: master’s dissertations, doctoral theses, scientific articles, and open access.

The descriptor “*educational tutelary measures*” yielded a total of 41 open-access results, one of which is from 1998, thus falling under the exclusion criteria for the time frame (2000-2021). Another result is categorized as a journal, which also falls under the exclusion criteria related to document type, as this research focused only on scientific articles, dissertations, and theses.

Seven documents were duplicates, and two documents deviated from the topic proposed by the research descriptor. In the end, there were 30 documents, which were divided into 19 master’s dissertations, eight scientific articles, and three doctoral theses. Regarding the fields of study of these documents, a table is provided below to illustrate:

Table 4 – Descriptor “educational tutelar measures”: fields of study of collected works

FIELD OF STUDY	NUMBER OF COLLECTED WORKS
Criminology	1
Education	2
Law	5
Physical Education	2
Political Science	1
Psychology	13
Sociology	6

Source: The Authors, 2024.

As can be observed, regarding the descriptor “*educational tutelary measures*,” the majority of the collected documents belong to the field of psychology, followed by law. These data illustrate the pathological nature of studies conducted in the field of Portuguese socioeducation, as well as the legal character of “*juvenile delinquency*.”

In order to proceed with the literature review, the decision was made to analyze the eight scientific articles gathered in this research. Among the three types of collected documents (dissertations, theses, scientific articles), it is preferable to focus on the

articles, as dissertations and theses are much longer and require a greater amount of time to thoroughly examine their content.

The texts to be analyzed are organized alphabetically in the table below:

Table 5 - Scientific articles related to educational tutelary measures

Title	Keywords	Field of study	Publication year
(Between) Perspectives on Female Delinquency	Children, youth, female delinquency, gender	Sociology	2013
Children, Youth, and the City: Risks, Violence, and Delinquency in Portugal	Children, youth, urban violence, delinquency, gender	Sociology	2013
Delinquency in Girls: Contributions to the Construction of a Typology of Transgressive Pathways	Female juvenile delinquency, transgressive pathways, sociological portraits, qualitative research	Sociology	2015
Family, Peers, and Juvenile Delinquency: Analysis of Different Recidivism Pathways	Educational tutelary measures, recidivism, risk factors, family, peer group	Psychology	2015
Historical Study of Social Reforms and the Protection of Marginalized Children: From the 19th Century to the Mid-20th Century	Social reform, child protection, marginalization, re-education of minors, image of the child	Education	2002
Intervention in Educational Centers: Discourses from Within	Perceptions, educational protective intervention, educational center, qualitative investigation	Sociology	2014
Pathways in Female Juvenile Delinquency: Contexts, Discourses, and Trajectories	No keywords	Sociology	2012
The Path of a Career: Opportunities for Young People Institutionalized in Portuguese Educational Centers	Professions; adolescents; educational centers	Psychology	2018

Source: The Authors, 2024.

Upon reviewing the aforementioned articles, the collected works were categorized for analysis: i) Family structure and dynamics: *Family, Peers, and Juvenile Delinquency: Analysis of Different Recidivism Pathways* ii) Gender (female): *Female Juvenile Delinquency from Multiple Perspectives: Contributions to the Construction of a Typology of Transgressive Pathways, Contexts, Discourses, and Pathways in Female Juvenile Delinquency, (Between) Perspectives on Female Delinquency* iii) Vocational psychology: *On the Path of a Career: Opportunities for Youth Institutionalized in Portuguese Educational Centers* iv) Perspectives of incarcerated youth and professionals in Educational Centers: *Intervention in Educational Centers: Discourses from Within* v)

Historical-socioeconomic context of juvenile “delinquency”: *Social Reforms and the Protection of Marginalized Children: A Historical Study from the 19th Century to the Mid-20th Century, Children, Youth, and the City: Risks, Violence, and Delinquency in Portugal.*

According to Ferreira (2021), who conducted a systematic literature review focused on the Brazilian socio-educational system, 37.93% (equivalent to 88 out of 215 published articles) were from the field of psychology. Similarly, in Portugal, based on the research conducted in this article, 13 of the collected journals are in the field of psychology (which accounts for 43.3% of the total works collected in this research), with a strong presence of pathologization and the creation of a stigma surrounding these adolescents.

There is also a noted scarcity of studies on family and peer groups and their influence on the lives of “delinquent” youth in Portuguese literature, as well as a predominance of male subjects in studies on “juvenile delinquency.”

In Portugal, the few qualitative studies conducted have primarily focused on the life trajectories of young people serving educational tutelary measures (Carvalho, 2003; Seabra, 2005; Duarte et al., 2004; Duarte, 2012), the dynamics within educational centers (Neves, 2008), or the social representations of youth regarding educational tutelary intervention (Manso, 2006). There is a noticeable bibliographic gap concerning studies involving professionals who work within the juvenile justice system (e.g., in courts, educational centers, and social reintegration teams) (Azevedo, Duarte, 2015).

This suggests that the issue of gender significantly influences this field, with girls and their specific needs frequently overlooked in the research. This presents a valuable opportunity for future studies. Furthermore, by downplaying the dynamics related to girls in the Portuguese socio-educational context, the system may fail to identify and adequately address potential weaknesses or the needs of the adolescents participating in the Educational Tutelary Measures program.

Final Considerations

This research highlights the disparity in the maintenance of data related to socio-education in Brazil and Portugal. In Portugal, the DGRSP is responsible for issuing monthly statistical reports on data from educational centers. In Brazil, Sinase (Brazil, 2006, 2012) publishes annual reports within a three-year interval, as mandated by law. However, it is important to note the difference in size and population between the two countries, which may be a contributing factor to this disparity.

Another point to note is the lack of data regarding the race and origin of adolescents in educational centers in Portugal. The statistical data from DGRSP reports show gender and age but do not specify race; they indicate origin but do not break down the category "foreigners." This raises concerns about what is not being revealed in these figures. Some of the studies collected in the research address topics such as gender and ethnicity; however, there is still a lack of data on these social characteristics in official government documents from Portugal.

The theme of socio-education and educational tutelary measures is rich and can still be studied and analyzed from various perspectives. The provocation presented in this work aims to inspire a curious examination of how countries in the Global North address their social issues and how countries in the Global South can enhance the measures used in their respective territories by reflecting on examples from geopolitically Northern countries. Furthermore, it is understood that differences arise from the geographical and political nature of these countries, particularly Brazil and Portugal in this text, thereby offering a different perspective for potential future studies.

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